

ApproxMath: Approximating Math Functions with Polynomial Series to Improve Performance on Accurate Hardware

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Abstract—We propose approximating transcendental math functions with polynomial Taylor series and Remez algorithm. These functions are by-definition approximation-tolerant, operating on floating-point data, and commonly used between applications. Although they occupy just a single code line, they are computed through a routine, taking a significant amount of cycles. We build towards an approximate math library with multiple accuracies that we obtain by changing the series order, and consequently reducing the number of instructions and required execution time on accurate, off-the-shelf processors. Our work is enabling a large and fine-grained design space with trade-offs between input range, accuracy, and performance.

Index Terms—Approximate computing, function approximation, embedded software.

I. INTRODUCTION

Approximate Computing (AxC) trades computation accuracy against energy or performance. A wide range of modern and prominent application domains, including recognition, data mining, synthesis, and semantic search, are shown to have a varying degree of resilience to errors, i.e., mismatches between their exact and approximate computation [1]–[3]. By relaxing the strict accuracy constraints in software and hardware, AxC techniques promise significant energy or performance improvements.

Despite promising improvements, several factors hinder the widespread adoption of AxC. For instance, the approximate hardware units are typically specialized both in function and also in accuracy [4]. Many systems utilize off-the-shelf components and cannot afford such specialized hardware modifications to embrace AxC techniques proposed by the research community [5]. A recent study from Facebook shows that 80% of machine learning workload on smartphones, a relatively hardware-accelerator-rich platform, is computed on general purpose CPUs, not on any kind of accelerator [6].

At the software level, there is a semantic gap of knowledge between AxC experts, who know the techniques and how to implement them, and the application experts, who can dissect the dataflow into sensitive and approximation tolerant parts. Although programming languages are extended to mark approximation tolerant variables [7] and operations [8], this fine-grained manual step significantly escalates the software design effort and also complexity. Moreover, these methods do not approximate and thus return any benefits by themselves; they are means to utilize other underlying approximations in software or, if supported, in hardware. In contrast, loop perforation is a general software technique that reduces the number of loops of iteratively refining algorithms to trade accuracy against performance. However, when it is compared in the x264 example, an algorithmic transformation of using sum of absolute differences without Hadamard operation shows a significantly better trade-off than loop perforation [9]. Such algorithmic transformations can improve performance with a small accuracy loss but they are specialized and require application expertise, not meant to be general and transferable to other applications.

Fig. 1. Approximation of $\sin(x)$ with Taylor series of order n .

In this paper, we propose approximating math functions towards building an approximate math library in multiple accuracies. We show that very commonly used functions, such as exponent, logarithm, square-root, and trigonometric functions can be approximated at different accuracies with Taylor series and Remez algorithm by varying the order, resulting in a varying number of iterations and execution time. They are transcendental functions, operating on floating-point data; by definition, they are approximation-tolerant since they are not expressible as a finite combination of the algebraic operations of addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, power, and root. Such math functions are often overlooked as they take a single line in the static program. However, unlike arithmetic operations, there is typically no direct function unit in hardware to execute them. In dynamic code, they are executed through a routine, which takes many cycles. We generate a large and fine-grained design space, in which the accuracy depends on the function, variable range and series order. Our work distinguishes from existing [10] by targeting compile-time modifications of any given code in C language towards finding the Pareto-optimal function in terms of performance for the set quality constraint. We make the following key contributions:

- We propose approximating math functions that are very commonly used, and thus have a large application space, and safe to approximate, operating on floating-point data.
- Our functions are completely in software, and hence can be deployed immediately to off-the-shelf hardware in a platform-independent manner. They are transferable between different architectures maintaining the same accuracy.
- The granularity of function-level approximation enables their drop-in replacement, without application expertise, with a fine-grain knob on accuracy vs. performance by changing the series order.

In our early experiments, for instance, we reduced the required execution time of `Black-Scholes` and `FFT` applications by 15% and 17% at an average relative error of 4% and 2%, respectively, on

Fig. 2. Approximate examples of $\cos(x)$, $\sin(x)$, $\exp(x)$, and $\log(x)$ math functions using Taylor series and Remez algorithm.

the final application output.

II. APPROXIMATE MATH FUNCTIONS

Taylor series and Remez algorithm are two mathematical methods for generating polynomial functions that can be used as approximations for math functions. Both methods calculate the coefficients of the polynomial expression differently. Taylor series uses a series expansion around a given point, using the function value and its derivatives at another point, while the Remez algorithm uses the minimax principle, selecting coefficients such as the maximum difference is the smallest possible. Figure 2 exemplifies approximate versions for four math functions obtained with these methods.

The trade-off between accuracy and execution time, $T_{\text{exec.}}$, for these approximations depends on:

Approximating method: As the $\cos(x)$ example in Figure 2 shows, the two methods achieve different accuracy. The polynomial obtained through the Taylor series produces a more accurate version than the Remez algorithm. For the $\sin(x)$ function, the opposite occurs.

Input interval of the function: As usual, the result of approximations are input dependent [5]. We observe a higher deviation with a broader input interval resulting in higher error for distant inputs. For instance, consider the input interval for $\sin(x)$ and $\exp(x)$ in Figure 2. In this case, the accuracy improves by using a higher-order polynomial, at a performance cost.

Polynomial order: Figure 1 shows that a higher-order polynomial fits the function for longer, hence improving the accuracy. However, a lower-order polynomial produces more savings in $T_{\text{exec.}}$. For instance, an order three polynomial function generated with Taylor series for $\sin(x)$ reduces $T_{\text{exec.}}$ in 40% w.r.t. the accurate function while one with order nine achieves 20%.

III. EVALUATION

We placed our approximate math functions in two applications of the AxBench [11] benchmark suite, Black-Scholes (using $\exp(x)$, $\log(x)$, and \sqrt{x}) and FFT (using $\sin(x)$ and $\cos(x)$), and used their given error metric. The approximate functions in Figure 2 are evaluated for the input interval required in these applications. To obtain the execution time, we used the performance counters of GVSOC RISC-V simulator [12].

Table I presents favorable performance vs. accuracy trade-offs in terms of execution time, $T_{\text{exec.}}$, vs. average relative error, ARE . For instance, we are able to reduce $T_{\text{exec.}}$ by 15% and 17% at a small accuracy degradation, 4% and 2% ARE in Black-Scholes and FFT, respectively.

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TABLE I
EVALUATION OF ERROR-TOLERANT APPLICATIONS WITH APPROXIMATE MATH FUNCTIONS.

$T_{\text{exec.}}$	ARE	$T_{\text{exec.}}$	ARE
0.95	0.015	0.99	0.010
0.92	0.030	0.92	0.015
0.85	0.040	0.83	0.020
0.79	0.079	0.78	0.090
0.74	0.081	0.70	0.100

(a) Black-Scholes

(b) FFT

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